

A GLANCE AT EMOTIONAL INFLUENCE OF THE POETRY

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ABSTRACT

This essay discusses poetry, how it came to be, the emotions that are reflected in it, and the poet's role in expressing those emotions. It also uses examples to focus on the inner spiritual experiences that the poet expresses in the poem.

Key words: Poetry, emotion, poetic techniques, verse, lyric poetry, dramatic poetry, narrative poetry, rhyme.

Poetry is a type of literature that aims to evoke an emotional response in the reader through language chosen and arranged for its meaning, sound, and rhythm. In particular, poems improve cognitive function, help heal emotional pain, lead to greater self-awareness and provide a gift of inspiration or education to others. According to the renowned Uzbek poet Erkin Vahidov, "the poem calms the reader's heart by expressing the essential emotions that were formed in the poet's heart". Here we report the discovery and characterization of a poem, the different types of poetry, poetry term definitions and how writers use poetic techniques to create images and stir emotions. Analyzing several poems, we try to show a combination of rhythm, word choice, sounds, rhymes, structure, meter and more to create a piece of writing that stirs the reader's feelings.

Some people associate poetry with subjectivity and the expression of intence personal experience. Alexander Pope once explained that he preferred to write poetry even when he wrote about philosophy.(Pope,Preface to An Essay on Man, 1734)[1], However, Uzbek poet Erkin Vahidov claims that "the poem calms the reader's heart by expressing the essential emotions that were formed in the poet's heart. Without burning himself, the poet cannot burn others, and without fire in his heart, he cannot warm the souls of others. All poetic silences, all artistic instruments, all artistic abilities are useless without this magical fire". (Erkin Vahidov, About poetry and life, 2002, Page 34)[2]. An American poet Robert Frost wrote-"No tears in the write, no tears in the reader".(Dr.Neena Sharma Conception in Poetry,The Criterion, Journal ISSN-0976-8165,Vol.II.Issue III)[3] In other words, emotion is the basis of poetry and the

deep hidden insights that the readers desire from you - those are the end products. Every poem, in my view, should express some form of sorrow, happiness, emotion, or thought, Otherwise, this poem will not be able to effectively influence, comprehend, or win the reader over.

A poem (Arabic: shuur - feeling) is an artistic work with a certain internal tone, created as an expression of thoughts mixed with feelings, expressed by exciting poetic speech. The word "verse" is sometimes used instead of the term "poem". Let's first look at history and civilization of the poet. With the development of cuneiform in Mesopotamia over 5000 years ago, poetry started to evolve. These poems, which were discovered on clay tablets, described the governing methods of the ancient rulers. Oral storytellers moved from one location to another as language spread in order to recite new myths and legends. Stanzaic verse most likely got its start as a sequence of deliberate pauses made by oral storytellers during their recitations. Since then, people have used hundreds or thousands of different poetic forms to express their interior and outer worlds, as well as the worlds of their peers, legends, and civilizations. Poetic development accelerated in periods of prolific creativity and in communities that were especially open, similar to how other forms of art and music did.

A lot has been said about poetry throughout the years. Aristotle's Poetics, one of the earliest definitions of poetry, placed particular emphasis on speech's functions in rhetoric, theater, song, and comedy. The aesthetics that set poetry apart from prose were emphasized in later efforts, which focused on elements like rhyme and repetition. Poetry has occasionally been loosely defined as a fundamentally creative act using words since the middle of the 20th century. To amplify the literal meaning of the words or to elicit emotional or sensual reactions, poetry frequently employs specific forms and conventions.

There are three main terms and so many different types of poems, and many have very few rules. We will talk about the terms and some of the most common types of poetry, their main characteristics, and famous examples of each. The most popular kind of poetry is **lyric poetry**, which includes haiku, odes, elegy, and limericks. Poetry that is **narrative** recounts a tale. Epic poems discuss historical events or conflicts, while ballads focus on a specific individual. In **dramatic poetry**, the plot is told by the actors. There is no fourth, novel method for artistically using words to convey reality that humanity has not yet found. However, one writing genre is hybrid. It exhibits traits common to both the song and epic genres. It is known as the Lyro-epic variety. This includes literary epics, poetic tales, poetic short stories, poetic novels, and literary tales adapted from folktales in a lyrical manner. (Pushkin "The Tale of Shah Sultan",

"Golden Fish and the tale of the old fisherman"...).The lyrical hero's inner experiences—those of love and hate, yearning and pain, dreams and sorrows, sorrows, and emotional thoughts—are primarily reflected in the lyrics. These emotions are more fully expressed in lyrics than in other literary forms.

Lyric Poetry typically explores your emotions and attitudes. The lyrics to a song are now frequently referred to as a lyric. The lyric poet addresses the reader directly, expressing personal emotions, thoughts, and views.

This composition is a sonnet and it has fourteen lines and adheres to the metrical pattern and rhyme system that are appropriate for that verse form. Wordsworth discusses industrialization in this song in a very passionate and personal way. Here are the poem's opening five lines:

The World is Too Much With Us (William Wordsworth)

The world is too much with us; late and soon,
Getting and spending, we lay waste our powers;—
Little we see in Nature that is ours;
We have given our hearts away, a sordid boon!
This Sea that bares her bosom to the moon;

Wordsworth expresses his anger and dismay over a general shift away from nature and in the direction of industry in his poem.

Humorous poems are funny poems and guaranteed to brighten your day.

A word to husbands (Ogden Nash)

To keep your marriage brimming
With love in the loving cup,
Whenever you wrong, admit it;
Whenever you're right, shut up.

Elegy, a reflective lyric poem lamenting the passing of a famous person, a companion, or a loved one; additionally, any contemplative song about the larger subject of mortality in human beings.

She Weeps over Ragoon (James Joyce)

Rain on Ragoon falls softly, softly falling,
Where my dark lover lies.
Sad is his voice that calls me, sadly calling,
At grey moonrise.

Love, hear thou
How soft, how sad his voice is ever calling,

Ever unanswered, and the dark rain falling,
Then as now.

Dark too our hearts, O love, shall lie and cold
As his sad heart has lain
Under the moongrey nettles, the black mould
And muttering rain.

Rhymes. The repetition of the same or similar sounds at the ends of two or more words, most frequently at the ends of lines, is a characteristic of **rhymes**, a form of poetry. Nursery rhymes frequently employ this method because it makes the song simple to recall.

Nature's way (John Pavano)

Upon a nice mid-spring **day**,
Let's take a look at Nature's **way**,
Breathe the scent of nice fresh **air**,
Feel the breeze within your **hair**.

It is clear that the primary purpose of a poem is to express to the reader a desire, pleasure, sadness, or dream, rather than simply to explain a subject. Even though there are many times fewer words in a poem than there are in a prose piece, some poems can evoke emotions and leave an impression that a full book cannot. In order for rhyme, rhythm, and words to naturally flow into the brain, the poet must be talented, have a broad perspective on the world, and have a heart that is full of love and sorrow and so his creations will continue to be included in the canon of poems that are lovedly read for ages.

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